

Vocational School Members' Responses to English Summative Mobile-Based Assessment during the Studying at Home Period

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ABSTRACT

The research aimed to reveal the responses of state vocational school members to English summative mobile-based assessment during the studying at home period. This kind of mobile-based assessment was administered due to the circular letter on the implementation of National Education in the time of Covid-19 emergency. Therefore, the school adopted the policy to carry out the summative assessment by using students' mobile device at home. The participants of this study were the stakeholder (vice principal of curriculum affairs), an English teacher, and three students. The data were collected through semi-structured interviews. The data were transcribed (write down verbatim) and analyzed inductively. The data analysis showed that except for certain cases, the schools members responded English summative mobile-based assessment positively. The responses varied from one participant to another. Above all, in the conclusion, advantages and disadvantages of the implementation of English summative mobile-based assessment emerged from the study.

1. Introduction

On March 16, 2020 the Indonesian Government announced the instruction to lock down in every part of the country due to the spread of Covid-19. Unquestionably, this policy was influential to education, economic, culture, and many other fields in Indonesia. Covid-19 has spread fast. People had to avoid any physical contact to others. They were banned to have a crowd and had to stay at home, so everybody was necessary to keep distancing physically and socially. Consequently, a lot of activities had to be done at home.

The biggest impact was education sector. It is not simple to change the education system in a short and quick time in such emergency situation. In this case the Education Minister, Mr.

Nadiem Anwar Makarim issued the Circular Letter Number 4 in 2020 on the implementation of National Education during the emergency of Coronavirus Disease (Covid-19). Regarding the Studying at Home period, the minister emphasized that the online learning/ distance learning is carried out to provide meaningful learning experience without any responsibility of demand to reach the entire curriculum. He added that this would apply to all regions which had implemented studying at home. It is very essential to keep the teachers' safety. Therefore, there were not any teaching and learning activities in class anymore. Teachers had to manage the learning process by online mode. The minister also suggested that the summative assessment be provided in the form of portfolio, tasks and online/distance assessment.

According to Alderson and Wall (1993) in Arslan and Ucok (2020), in dealing with the policy changes, teachers must know the motives and logical considerations because their power to control is to transfer the changes to the classrooms. So, it is obvious that assessment is able to assist to know what exactly occurs in the classrooms because it is conceived that the description of teaching practices and opinion about language teaching and learning is shown on the way they choose the techniques and tools of language assessment. In this context, it is worthwhile to consider the circular letter to carry out the summative assessment of the even semester by using mobile-based test. By means of these considerations, it insists to carry out a school program as a new policy, and it certainly effects to some sectors in the institution. Response or reaction to this new system of assessment can emerge among the members of school because it has never been conducted previously. This new policy implementation may result in either positive or negative responses.

Wang (2018) states that a qualitative study searches personal views, experiences, responses, perceptions, concepts, and pearls of wisdom and define the context in detail. Dealing with the perspective, school members' response was chosen as the topic of this study. The current study aimed to investigate the responses of the school members at State Vocational School 1 of Banyumas in Central Java, Indonesia to English summative mobile-based assessment implemented during the studying at home period. Its purpose was to answer the question: "What are the responses of the school members at State Vocational School 1 of Banyumas in the 2019/2020 academic year to English summative mobile-based assessment?"

2. Literature Review

2.1 People's Responses

The policy to administer summative mobile-based assessment certainly considered many aspects. The stakeholder also thought about the responses from the school members. Mobile-based assessment was the best choice in the pandemic of Covid 19. Therefore all of the subjects were tested including English by using students' mobile phone/android from their home with an application created by the school. However it could be predicted that there would be positive and negative responses from the school members. According to Richards and Schmidt (2002, p. 514) "A response is the behaviour which is produced as a reaction to a stimulus." While Paulina (2002) as cited in Sumilia et al. (2019) proposes that response is behavioural act, response comes as a result of the entry into the same mind of stimulus with the sense of someone. In this case the stimulus was the implementation of summative mobile-based assessment as the new system.

A study shows that the choice of a specific testing model would raise reaction from the teachers and the students. From the teacher's point of view, it motivated their teaching improvement by updating the testing techniques. While for the students, it would make them feel in mixed emotions like scare, unfairness, bias, pressure and suspicion (Xiao & Carless, 2013). According to Dörnyei and Ushioda (2011) in Xiao and Carless, "Assessment can also provide motivation and encouragement when results are good. Satisfaction often follows from positive experiences, such as praise or good marks." In this case any kind of testing enables everyone at school to react positively and negatively. Xiao & Carless (2013) add some affective responses can be induced to the students after they recognize the scores of their summative assessment. When they got good result, certainly they would feel satisfaction and they would have the sense of achievement. Otherwise, the students would feel suppressed or feel worried if they achieved a bad result.

2.2 The Summative Assessment

In English Language Teaching (ELT), the term of assessment has a general meaning. According to Brown (2003) assessment is always available in the process of teaching and learning therefore the activity is continuing to develop and it is wider than a test. In other words, the teachers can make an assessment such as the students perform to deliver their opinion, give answer or check the words or structure. Blercom (2009) states that assessment constitutes the ways to analyse and evaluate how the students behave and how well they are as long as in the teaching and learning.

There are some various assessments in ELT. Brown (2003) mentions that from the view point of function, there are two kinds of assessment tests; formative and summative. Summative test is defined as "a test given at the end of a course of instruction that measures or "sums up" how much a student has learned from the course." (Richards & Schmidt, 2002, p. 529). Brown (2003) states that the objectives of summative assessment is analysis and expressing the most important facts about the students' comprehension on what they have obtained in short and clear form at the end of the learning period. Blercom (2009) suggests that summative assessment functions are to decide the standard ability with the competencies and give grades. To put it in other words, the students take the summative test to determine how much they have acquired certain competencies at the end of a learning period (six months). As a routine the teachers arrange some assessment items after completing a course to deliver as a summative test for a learning period or a semester. The parents will then receive the score report for the semester's learning outcomes.

The Indonesia's recent curriculum *Kurikulum 2013* (Discovery Learning) has implemented the authentic assessment as the part of curriculum system in teaching and learning. This informal assessment is used to analyse and evaluate the input, process and output of learning concerning to affective, cognitive, and psychometric dimensions which are then taken into account to recognize the learning level and learning characteristics of the students. Therefore the authentic assessment is carried out along the teaching and learning process, from the beginning up to the end continuously and lasting for a long time (Suwartono & Riyani, 2019). Moreover, summative assessment is categorized into cognitive domain. On the other hand, the assessment system in the context of Indonesia mostly uses Bloom's taxonomy as a cognitive based assessment system (Irwansyah, 2018). There are six levels of the revised taxonomy; remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating, and creating.

A previous study reveals the importance of language assessment. For students to learn a language, assessment is very crucial. It plays a key role in the learning process and, using their current skills, exposes students to new information (Tosuncuoglu, 2018). So the assessment is designed to measure to what extent they learn the language for a particular skill. Additionally, the assessment can be designed in the form of multiple choice tests. The main point that should be considered is the practicality and reliability of the assessment items (Brown, 2003). It is time consuming to write the assessment items but for the teacher is easier to score and to grade. Moreover, it is time saving to check the answers.

However, it is obvious that multiple choice items have some weaknesses. According to Brown (2003) the weaknesses are;

1. Technically it assesses only cognitive dimension.
2. Students may only suspect the answers from the choices so it causes to interfere in the scores.
3. The method is very seriously limited on what can be tested
4. Designing a good item is very hard to do.
5. "The positive or negative impact of a test on classroom teaching or learning (backwash)" (Richards & Schmidt, 2002, p. 586) may be dangerous.
6. It is possible for the students to do the test dishonestly.

A recent study states that the most well-known type of assessment is Multiple Choice Questions Test which has been implemented by a lot of English teachers in Indonesia (Rachmat & Arfiandhani, 2019). Brown (2003, p. 56) explains the characteristic of Multiple-Choice Items:

1. Receptive or selective. It must supply responses but it does not allow creating one.
2. Each of items has a stem to present a stimulus, and several options/alternatives choose.
3. One as the key of the correct answer and the others as distractors.

Although they have certain disadvantages, multiple choice questions are the most popular test item used by teachers through to the perspectives. It will be the most straightforward and suitable form of test item in the COVID-19 period by taking certain factors into account.

2.3 Information and Communication Technology (ICT)

As a matter of fact, some ways can be considered to administer the summative assessment such as paper based test, computer based test or mobile based test. Each of these techniques will have its advantages and disadvantages. For the last decades recently, computer based test has been very well-known. And nowadays mobile based assessment is more popular in English learning teaching. Suwartono and Aniuranti (2018) suggest that English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers should warmly welcome the development of technology and using it optimally as a tool to promote their teaching and learning. Nevertheless, some studies reveal that there are some potential problems of mobile devices such as inadequate connectivity, insufficient memory, and so forth, as Elaish et.al (2017) mentions, "Internet connection speed, and examinations on mobiles are other cumbersome problems that need to be resolved."

According to Ahmed et al. (2020) as cited in Bin-Hady et.al (2020) the introduction of technology has provided many opportunities to learn easily and rapidly for students. Moreover it has provided learners more accountability and autonomous learning positions in almost instructor-free learning environments to tackle their language learning regardless of time and location.

According to Yarahmadzahi & Goodarzi (2020) "One area of language learning and teaching classes which can be influenced by technology usage is assessment." It is simpler because the students can do test inside or outside the classroom and it can be implemented into some kinds of assessments such as formative, self-assessment and peer assessment, classroom polling, summative and many others (Yarahmadzahi & Goodarzi, 2020). Nikou and Aconomides (2018) add that when the assessment applying makes use of Mobile-Based Assessment (MBA), the students may use the personal electronic mobile devices like Personal Digital Assistants, smart phones or tablets.

It obvious that the availability and advancement of ICT has been an essential portion in ELT especially for the online learning era in the pandemic of Covid-19. As we know, most teenagers in this global era are very familiar with mobile phone. They use it not only to communicate but also to utilize many other applications purposes like social media, games, office tools, browser, and so forth. Without any doubt the technology development has been inspiring the teaching and learning activity which will involve assessment. Many kinds of assessment in English today take the advantages of technology. The usage of Mobile-Based Assessment starts to be a new different mode after paper or computer-based assessment. Therefore, conducting summative assessment by using mobile-based test is not a difficult problem for the students.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Participants

This is descriptive case study in which data were collected through semi-structured interviews. A descriptive case study sets out, for example, what various techniques are used by a reader and how the reader uses them to explain the natural phenomena that exist within the data in question (Yin, 1984). In other words, the corniest phase of a case study is descriptive in its nature (Yin, 2004). It has some essential characteristics such as describing the relevant individuals and organizations that are interested in the issue and their actions, feelings, and opinions. Then it usually concentrates on a limited number of persons or classes.

Furthermore, case studies analyse, evaluate and describe the real-life, difficult lively and opening behaviour of events, human relationships and other factors because contexts are unusual and lively (Cohen et al., 2011). Richard & Schmidt (2002, p. 64) propose a case study as "the intensive study of an aspect of behaviour, either at one period in time or over a long period of time."

The research context is the English summative assessment at the even semester at State Vocational School 1 of Banyumas, in Central Java, Indonesia. The participants of this study are the Vice Principal of curriculum as stakeholder, an English teacher, and three students.

3.2 Data Collection

In this study, the data were collected through semi-structured interviews to the participants. The interviews were conducted via voice note due to the situation of pandemic. Then the voice notes were transcribed. They were written down word by word (verbatim). Transcripts can provide important details and important verbatim record of the interview. In this case the transcripts of the stakeholder and the English teacher were served based on themes regarding each question.

To ensure the validity of the data, the participants were requested to read the transcripts. Golafshani (2003) describes that the validity is a requirement for a research on some kinds of qualifying check or measure. He adds that it is used to reduce the bias and enhance the honesty of the researcher.

3.3 Data Analysis

The transcripts then was analysed inductively to reveal the participants' responses. Creswell (2014) states "This inductive process illustrates working back and forth between the themes and the database until the researchers have established a comprehensive set of themes." It means that it was needed to analyse the data by skimming the themes and the database many times in order to obtain the comprehensive collection of themes.

In order to make the analysis simpler, the data were divided into three parts. The first data were from the Vice Principal as the stakeholder with various themes and the code was VP. The second one was the English teacher with some themes and the code was ET. The last was the data from the three students. It used alphabets like A, B, C to indicate the participants. Thus the initials for students who participated in this research are S.A (student A), S.B (student B), and S.C (student C). It was also made themes based on the questions for the students' interview. This effort was taken because in qualitative approach it is required to help the researcher analyse and categorize the data in order to identify similar information.

4. Findings

Based on the problems under study, some findings are presented here.

4.1. The responses of the school members to English summative mobile-based assessment

Vice Principal (VP) as stakeholder

The considerations

With regard to the considerations to carry out the summative assessment virtually, the VP mentioned four considerations. The main factor was Covid-19 and the limitation on social distancing. He also notified the appeal to decrease the paper usage for an assessment test, and it affordable since it didn't need much fund to administer the assessment by using mobile phone. These were in line with the result of the interview. He said:

"The main factor was the pandemic of Covid-19, so it's forbidden to have a crowd. It's recommended to have paperless assessment in this teaching-learning era. It refers to the circular letter from the education Minister. It is the continuity of the online learning before. It costs less in expense and committee."

The application of the summative mobile-based assessment

Next, dealing with the applications prepared for the summative assessment, the VP said that it was a special application which could be operated easily and it was designed so that the students were not able to open the other applications to minimize the chance to do the test dishonestly. The VP explained:

"It is a special application. It's familiar software so it's easy to be applied to the students. They can open it easily but they cannot open the other applications or browse something. In this case there was a little chance to cheat but there is anticipation to it as well. When the students would like to cheat by opening the browser, at the same time they would get a trouble automatically. Server warned them and they would miss the connection from the server. So the admin would know that the students do cheating. Actually, the application can be operated through browser, but it should be updated first. Otherwise, the items and the options were disappeared."

The access of the application.

The VP also explained that the students operated the application with a link provided by the server then they connected into it. After that they completed the test. VP said:

"The students got the link from the server. Without the link, they couldn't do the test. Students could tap the application on their mobile phone, access the link, read the items and then choose the best answer by clicking/ tapping the options provided."

Advantages and disadvantages

The advantages and disadvantages of using mobile-based assessment were revealed by the VP. He mentioned some advantages such as

- a. Students could do the assessment from home.
- b. The teacher could acquire the score directly after the assessment. It's efficient because they didn't take time to check the answer.
- c. It's very easy to be operated.
- d. It cost less money because it was paperless. The items were in the form of digital. The schools did not need to afford any expense to copy the items.
- e. The admin could get the score directly and distributed it to the teacher respectively.

While the disadvantages were that *"it's an online assessment so it couldn't control on the spot. The students did the test at home. Doing the test dishonestly depended much on the students, however school emphasizes that they had to do the assessment honestly by themselves because the supervisor didn't implement a remote proctoring."*

English Teacher

The second participant is the English teacher (ET). He responded all the questions well and as it was.

The school's policy

As one of the school members, the ET gave his agreement to the school's policy to administer mobile-based assessment due to the pandemic situation. He said:

"I do agree with the policy because there is no other choice to do this assessment in this epidemic situation. So that's not a problem for the school to apply/implement this kind of mechanism by applying this kind of summative test. I think that's good for the school to do that."

The application

According to the ET, the application used in the assessment was suitable because of the features provided in it. He responded:

"Yes, there are some applications that support this function and I think so far so good. That's good because it is completed with so many features."

The Score

For further question, the teacher did not give definite response to the students' scores because the situation is very different. He argued that he couldn't distinguish the result of the summative assessment in this situation with the previous one because the teaching-learning system was different. Regarding to the score, the ET said:

"We cannot compare the result of the test in this situation to the previous time. I mean in the normal situation, we cannot compare to the situation today because the material cannot be delivered well. In this situation, we simply rely on the online classes but in normal school, we can interact, we can understand what the biggest problem those students face. We can give the closer treatment to the student. Today we cannot do that. We cannot compare nor do the same treatment in this situation."

Submitting Process

Actually, there were some problems occurred when the students did the assessment. One of them was the process of submitting the answers. In this case the ET understood the cause of the problem in which numbers of students could not submit the answers, and he said:

"So many students failed to do that because I am teaching in vocational high school and my students come from various economic backgrounds. They got so many problems including the financial to buy the internet data."

Choosing the mode or system of the English summative assessment

In general, schools could administer an assessment with online or offline mode. They were done by using computer/laptop based test or mobile-based test for online mode, and paper based test for offline mode. Dealing with the system, the ET preferred to conduct paper based test at school rather than mobile-based test at home because by this mean, he could interact with the students directly and control their attitude during the assessment test. He explained:

"Paper based test is still not the best but better for the teacher to give the assessment because we can interact with the student. We can see the process on how the test run so we can see whether the students are really able to that, whether the students do it by themselves or not. When we apply the test using mobile phone, I still found so many cases that the students tried to look for the answer from the sources or the internet or just copy the text then put it on the Google translate in order to recognise the meaning."

Advantages and disadvantages

Regarding the advantages and disadvantages of using a mobile-based assessment for the summative assessment, the English teacher had his own viewpoint. He explained:

"The use of the application will force the students to have the ability to understand the mechanism how to operate it because most of the applications using English as their manual. So, when the students try to do the assignment for example, they will try to familiarize themselves how to use it, how to upload, how to give the comment. As I said before that not all the students have good access to it. I mean most of the students don't have internet data. Some of them even don't have a smartphone. So we cannot do the same treatment because they have different capability in this."

Student

There were three students for the third category of the participant. They gave various responses for each of the questions related to the English summative mobile-based assessment. The responses were delivered according to some themes based on the questions of the interview.

Feeling before the test

The three students had different feeling before they do the test. Two of them felt happy, but another one expressed it ordinarily. SA said:

"I feel happy and a little worries",

And SB stated:

"I am happy"

His expression was audible from his tone that he was absolutely happy. Otherwise SC said:

"It's nothing."

She expressed her feeling without any pressure.

Prediction on the new system of the test

When the school announced a new regulation, the students usually had their own prediction of the case. Each of the students mentioned different prediction such as the form of the test, the emergence of technical problem with the connection, and the possibility of getting the same type of assessment test like he did in Junior High School. SA responded:

"I imagine the test may only consist of Multiple Choice Question so it's a little easy for me to do because there are no essay questions."

Then SB said:

"I imagine there might be networking or technical problem and the limitation of internet data."

While SC said:

"I can imagine the test is simply like National Examination when I was in Junior High School. Just click the answer."

Preparation for the summative assessment

For the next question, the students responded it based on their habitual in learning. Generally, they prepared the test by learning the material. On the other hand, SB also prepared the test by supplying the internet data and SC downloaded the application of Google Translate to find out the meaning of difficult words. SA stated:

"I prepared the English test by learning the material. I also prepared data for the internet to do the English test and the other subjects. I tried to find the best place to get good connection."

Then SB said:

"Learn and supply the internet data."

And SC answered:

"I learnt again the tasks and the materials from my teacher download Google Translate to be used to find the meaning of words which I haven't known."

Intention of cheating

One of the problems in conducting online test was that the teacher couldn't control the students' attitude during the test. They did it at home by using their mobile phone without remote controlling from the school. So it was probably happened that some of them did the test dishonestly. In this case SA and SB had ever thought to do so but in fact they preferred to be honest in completing the test. Otherwise SC concerned to translate the items with the aid of Google translates. SA answered:

"I ever thought about looking at the book and finding the answer from Google when I did the test."

Then SB added:

"I have ever thought about that but still I considered being honest and doing the test by myself."

While SC said:

"I tend to focus on the application of Google translate."

Family supports

As a matter of fact another key factor of education especially in Indonesia was parents. Vocational students as teenagers depend much on the family support to their study. The family usually encouraged them by facilitating both material and morale. The three participants obtained the same attention from their parents, such as giving time and space to do the test, providing fund to buy the internet data, and also remind them to learn the subject's materials. SA mentioned:

"My parents supported me to learn and do the test by giving time from the beginning up to the end of the test."

And SB said;

"My family supported me by giving the expense to buy internet data and asked me to learn."

While SC responded:

"They supported me with prayer and my mother always woke me up to learn early in the morning."

Feeling doing the test at home

With regard to the question, the students gave the same responses. They felt comfortable when doing the test at home because they were relaxed and excited. SA answered:

"I felt more relaxed when I did summative assessment at home."

SB said:

"I felt excited because it's more comfortable." And SC said:

"I felt calmer and relaxed."

Feeling during the English Assessment

The participants gave different responses to this question. SA felt that English assessment was the same as the others, but SB thought that it was easy. Otherwise, according to SC, he felt more relaxed during the test. SA stated:

"When doing the English assessment, my feeling was the same as I did the other subjects test. I had ever thought to open the application to translate the difficult words in my mobile phone."

SB said:

"I felt nothing. The test was easy."

And SC answered:

"I felt more relax. Although there was a chance to ask to friends but I prefer to focus on Google translate whenever I got difficulties."

Technical problem during implementation

Obviously, technical problem occurred during the assessment such as disconnecting with the networking or slow response with the server. SA had got a problem with the server; however SB and SC didn't have any problem.

SA explained:

"Technically there was a problem with a server. It's slowly respond. So when I wanted to jump into the next item, I had to wait for some minutes to do it. Sometimes the networking of my hand phone was not so good.",

Then SB said:

"No difficulties."

While SC answered:

"I hadn't got any problem with the signal or my android."

Submission Process

Submission was the essential part in doing the test. If the students failed to submit, they would not get any score. Fortunately all the participants in this study had been successful in submission process.

SA expressed:

"I succeed send the answer."

Then SB said:

"I send the answer successfully."

And SC said:

"Alhamdulillah, I was successful."

Choice on the mode system

This was the first experience for them having summative mobile-based assessment at home. Previously, the school always administered paper based test at school. The three respondents gave their own preferences on the mode system like SA preferred to do paper based test at school, however SB and SC chose the mode system of the test by using mobile-based assessment at home. Relating to this question, SA said:

"I chose paper based test at school rather than mobile-based test at home. I could focus on the items better at school than at home."

SB said:

"I choose the mobile-based test at home because I feel more comfortable and it's practical."

And SC answered:

"I prefer mobile-based assessment at home"

The place in which students are able to focus on the assessment

The place to administer the summative assessment determined the students' comfort in doing the test. Since the pandemic situation didn't allow the students come to school, so they had to do the assessment from home. However, SA mentioned that she was able to concern on the test more at school than at home. In contrary, SB and SC were able to focus on the test at home. SA explained:

"I could focus on the test well at school compare to do it at home, because there might be networking problem at home."

SB shared:

"I could focus more in doing the test at home because when I did it in class; I always looked at my friends who had finished doing the test early."

SC said:

"I was focus more doing the assessment at home because it's quieter, relax, and unnerve as if seeing other friends finished doing the test at school."

Feeling after the test

The three participants responded in different expressions after doing the assessment. The one who felt satisfied was SC due to the higher score. SA expressed:

"I felt less satisfied with the result."

Then SB said:

"I felt dissatisfied",

And SC responded:

"I felt satisfy, this was my higher grade compared to the X level."

Advantages and disadvantages

The students shared their responses about the advantages and disadvantages of using a mobile-based assessment for the summative assessment. SA said:

"It can be done a little bit relax and I can do another work at the same time but It is bothered maybe by the bad signal. So I have to be patient."

While SB stated:

"I feel comfortable to do the test, although I have to provide the internet data."

And SC explained:

"It is easy to do because I just click and click the answer. I am sure my choices are right because I can see the references from books or internet. There is no any disadvantage because the items of the test are easy to be done."

5. Discussion

Some findings mentioned above are worth discussing here.

Vice Principal of Curriculum

The consideration to carry out the summative assessment using mobile phone

After analysing the data of the transcriptions, it was revealed that Vice Principal of curriculum expresses positive responses to summative mobile-based assessment. It was shown that the stakeholder gave much attention to the Minister's circular letter. He handled it well and seriously. With regard to the circular letter published by Education Minister, the final assessment of the even semester can be administered using online test or long-distance assessment (Makarim, 2020). Significantly the school then proposed a model of summative assessment that could be done by the students at home. All things considered were the emergency situation and the importance of assessment. As a recent study revealed that assessment was so essential that the students enable to receive a language thus it performed necessary position in the teaching-learning activities and related students to the new knowledge utilizing their current competences (Tosuncuoglu, 2018).

The application of the mobile-based assessment

As the consequence of this decision, the stakeholder discontinued to create an application which was compatible with the students' device. They designed a special application which could be operated by mobile phone or android. In short, he emphasized that this application was proper to conduct the summative assessment during SFH because it could measure what should be measured and the students could access it with a little effort. As Richards & Schmidt (2002, p. 529) state, the teacher can measure and decide how large the students have learned the competence at the end of a course by using a summative test.

The procedure to access the application

As a matter of fact, it is usual for the students as teenagers to operate their own mobile phone. As Ahmed et al. (2020) in Bin-Hady et.al (2020) state, the occurrence of technology has invented some chances for the students to learn simply and fast therefore they have obtained more responsibility and autonomous learning roles. Hence, the stakeholder has considered about the simple way to utilize the application of mobile-based assessment.

English Teacher

Feeling of responding to the school's policy

He reacted positively to the English summative mobile-based assessment. He argued that using mobile phone to do the assessment was a good choice in the pandemic situation. His sentences indicated positive response to support the policy. As Xiao & Carless (2013) propose, the choice on a testing model is able to motivate the teaching enhancement by updating the testing technique.

Opinion about the application

Referring to his opinion, it is not a problem for the teacher to apply any kinds of platform such as Google Classroom, Edmodo, and so forth for the online learning. The entire platforms provide many features including assignment, the test, uploading media, audio, video or file. As Suwartono and Anjuranti (2018) propose, it is better for the teachers to use media as their tools in teaching-learning process. Thus the teacher just simply opens the work from the students using the media and gives the correction or score on the application. In addition he gave good response dealing with the English summative mobile-based assessment application used at that time.

Responses to the Score

However, as an English teacher, he felt that it was a big difficulty for him to deliver the material because the presence of the teacher in the class was still important rather than applying or using the mobile-based test. In this case he had negative feeling about it. The student's score were surely different compared to the offline class. He didn't have much power to control the students from the distance not only with the learning process but also with the assessment. By this negative reaction, it is obvious that the selection of specific technique model would emerge reaction from the students and the teacher (Xiao & Carless, 2013)

Submission process

The teacher was very surprised when the students was not successful in submitting the answers. However, he realized it happened due to the student's condition. Related to this obstacle, Elaish et al. (2017) emphasizes that mobile devices have some potential problems, like internet connection speed and especially for those who are in the rural and remote area, it will have less access.

Mode or system of the English summative assessment

In this context, the teacher tended to choose paper based assessment because of the pedagogical reasons and the practicality aspect of the test. As Brown (2003) states, the practicality of the assessment test is the main point to be considered.

Student

After analyzing the data, it was indicated that two students responded positively, and it was a common thing for the second student having the assessment using online mode. However, all of them showed behavioral act by responding the stimulus given (Paulina, 2002 in Sumilia et al., 2019).

For the next question, the three students could imagine how they would do with the test because they had experiences when they were at the junior high school. It was easy for them to do the MCQ (multiple Choice Questions). However, one student could imagine that there would be a technical problem. Their responses showed that they like MCQ better than Essay Questions. It refers to the characteristic of MCQ as Brown (2003) suggests that MCQ provide the options, so the students don't create the answer, and a stimulus is given before the options.

Generally, they prepared the same things before they did the assessment such as learning the material, download the Google translate, supply the internet data and also find the best place to get good connection. Mobile-based assessment in the form of MCQ takes much risk or potentially gives the opportunity to cheat. Brown (2013) states the weaknesses of MCQ; one of them is the possibility to do the test dishonestly. The students gave different responses about it. Actually it depends much on their behavior. The two students had the opportunity to do so but they still thought about doing the test honestly with their competence. The last student usually consulted his problem with Google translate which really contrary to the teacher. He didn't realize if he had done the forbidden thing.

As a matter of fact, their parents and family supported their needs to be successful in the assessment with online mode. Their parents supported them by giving the expense to buy internet data, gave time to do the test from the beginning up to the end and also encourage them to learn. By these motivations, the students felt comfortable when they did the assessment. Their involvement is very beneficial to encourage their learning.

The three participants gave different responses on the implementation of the English summative assessment at that time. Two of them said that there were not any difficulties. Another one said that she had got a problem with her mobile phone because sometimes the networking was not good. Technically she also had a problem with the server. It's slowly respond, so when she wanted to jump into the next item, she had to wait for some minutes.

As Elaish et al (2017) states that few of the heavy problems technically are internet connection speed and examinations on using mobile devices that require the solution. Since the participants live in a rural and remote area, it has limitation of access.

Concerning the best place to do the assessment, SB and SC preferred to do mobile-based assessment at home due to the comfortably situation. They emphasized that they could concern well at home. It was really different from SA and the English teacher. This case indicated that some students do not like to be controlled directly by the teacher when they are doing an assessment in class. Nevertheless, concerning to the submitting process, they were all successful to submit the answer. According to Xiao & Carless (2013) the students would feel satisfied after they recognized the result of their summative assessment. When they got high score, they would feel satisfied, on the other hand if they got bad score, they would get suppressed and worrying.

Above all, it can be seen that SA, SB, and SC gave some positive and negative responses for some questions variously as well.

On the other hand, the researcher also revealed some advantages and disadvantages of the English summative mobile-based assessment implementation from the participants' interview. As for the advantages, some studies have revealed that mobile devices are proved to be very beneficial in learning and teaching activities. The rapid development of mobile technology has provided many advantages to the teachers as well as the students since it gives a lot of functions with its characteristics such as practicality, mobility, portability, interactivity, flexibility, and so forth (Nikou & Economides 2013; Almaiah, Masita & Man 2016). As we know that in this online learning era, mobile devices can be used anytime and anywhere. The teachers are able to access teaching materials, interact or communicate with the students and also conduct an assessment. In other words, mobile-based assessment can also save expense due to the paperless.

6. Conclusion

Based on the result and discussion above, it can be concluded that most of the vocational school members respond to the English summative mobile-based assessment positively. The VP responses indicated that the school has decided suitable solution in the emergency situation of Covid 19. Furthermore, along with the technological development, it was deservedly to employ the technological tools to administer summative assessment. Meanwhile, the positive response from the English teacher constitutes a commitment that digital technology has many advantages to the EFL learning including the assessment. Additionally the student's responses showed that they accepted the school policy. There were not any problems when they operated the system during the test. The technological development is much closer to their daily life. They are accustomed to use the mobile device. So, the summative mobile-based assessment was the proper system to be implemented by this situation.

However, it commonly happened if there were still negative responses to the implementation of new system. They were about the case of technical aspect from the stakeholder and the practicality aspect of an assessment from the English teacher. By all means, the researcher can obtain the advantages and disadvantages of the implementation in the assessment. The advantages are the assessment can be conducted by using students' mobile phone so they

can do it at home. It saves the expense due to the paperless. The disadvantages are the assessment cannot be controlled by the teacher directly because the students do it at home and the lack of supported devices or internet data.

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